

THE TRADITIONAL SONNET GENRE AND ITS LINGUOPOETICS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract: This article mainly deals with the sonnet genre and its linguo-poetics in English literature.

Key words: Artistic style, Sonnet, artistic speech, the term "Sonnet", musical art, love sonnet, system of symbols, artistic fabric, writer's fantasy, prose, poetry, drama, genre.

The sonnet is the first form of poetry to emerge as a written genre since ancient times, bypassing musical performance. A sonnet talks about love, analyzes experienced feelings, describes experiences and hopes. The poet confesses his love for a woman and glorifies the highest beauty and goodness. The sonnet originated as a genre of self-knowledge. Sonnet is a type (genre) of lyrics, the main feature of which is the size of the text.

The term "sonnet" is literally translated as "song" and means a verse consisting of 14 lines grouped in a strictly defined order. Conventionally, a sonnet can be divided into two quatrains and two triplets, where a total of five rhymes are used, two in quatrains and three in tercets (triplets).

In terms of content, the sonnet is based on a certain sequence of thought development: thesis - antithesis - synthesis - rebuttal. However, this principle is not always followed. A sonnet should be closed with a "sonnet lock". The theme hidden in the sonnet is usually located in the last two lines, rarely in one. In a lyric poem, this is a paradox, a phrase that contains an unexpected conclusion. In the theme of the lyrical-epic sonnet hidden in the sonnet, the author should lead the action of the plot unexpectedly. As a rule, the small volume of the topic hidden in the sonnet determines the possibilities of the final phrase, the aphorism. A special semantic emphasis falls on the last word in the sonnet: it is the "key" and often determines the meaning of the entire sonnet. If a riddle is hidden in a sonnet, then the word "key" will lead to the correct answer. This last word in the text may be the name of the subject of the sonnet.

The term "sonnet" itself (from the word sonnet-song) has a hint that it is a "sound" poetic form. In this regard, special importance is attached to the musicality of the sonnet. It was once said by L.G. Grossman, one of the researchers of the genre, said so. Musicality is an integral attribute of the sonnet. This is achieved in part by alternating pronouns with stress on the last word of a line and stress on the second syllable from the end of a line. There is also a certain norm of joints. An ideal sonnet should have 154 syllables, and the number of syllables in quatrains should be one more than in tercets.

The sonnet occupies an important place in Renaissance literature. The history of this term indicates the complex process of origin and borrowing of this lyrical genre. Also, during this period, the sonnet became the leading genre of lyric poetry. Almost all the poets of the Renaissance turned to him: P. Ronsard, J. Du Bellay, Lope de Vega, L. Camoes, V. Shakespeare, even Michelangelo and Mary Stewart.

In their works, the sonnet finally acquired its own important features: autobiography, intellectualism, lyricism. In sonnets, especially in sonnet cycles, the maximum rapprochement of the author and the lyrical hero is felt. The sonnet is a response to the poet's experiences. Also, sonnets are often occasionally written as poems.

Thus, in terms of content, we can single out a few of the most characteristic changes:

- 1) Love sonnet. He undoubtedly dominates the writers of sonnets, rising from extreme emotions, describing his lover and his alter ego.
- 2) Sonnet is a poetic manifesto. In such sonnets, he expresses his poetic inclinations.
- 3) Sonnet initiation called to life by a specific person or event.
- 4) Sonnet-mythology is a poem in which one or more images are developed, taken from legends, traditions.
- 5) Ironic sonnet. Many poets, as if arguing with the solemnity of the genre, made a mockery of the sonnet. The theoretical understanding of the sonnet genre became widespread in the 17th century. Thus, Nicholas Boleo devoted several lines to the praise of the sonnet in "Poetic Art", a manifesto of classicism. In addition, Boleo theoretically strengthened the practice of creating sonnets, his theories became the pioneer.

August Wilhelm Schlegel, one of the founders and theoreticians of German Romanticism, gives a brief definition of the sonnet canon:

I knitted two squares with one chain,
I combine two couplets into two rhymes,
I frame the second pair of the first,
To make a double shift sound.

Escaping from captivity in the verse

I already arrange rhymes more freely,
But courage, do I glorify love
I leave the number and order unchanged.

Who rejected my strophic law,
Who thought it was a meaningless game,
It is not included in the sonnet caste.

Those who are charmed by my magic, I unfold breadth and depth in solid form And in symmetry I unite all contrasts.

The sonnet is one of the most traditional lyrical genres of European literature, but for seven centuries it has not lost its appeal. The word sonnet (nov. sonetus, it. sonetto) is a form derived from Latin. formed by sonos (old. son - "tone", "sound") and diminutive suffixes. Sonnet is translated from Italian as "song". A sonnet is a 14-line lyrical poem written in quatrain or pentacle iambic. The sonnet originated in Italy in Ser. The 13th century and its prosperity are associated with the works of Dante and Petrarch. Here, an Italian sonnet pattern consisting of 2 quatrains (4-line stanzas with cross-rhyming) and 2 tercets (3-line stanzas) was developed. In the 16th century. passed from Italian poetry to French and quickly spread throughout Europe. By the Renaissance, the two types of sonnet canon, French and Italian, were finally defined.

It is known that the artistic text appears as a product of the creative aesthetic perception of the world and reality. The creation of an artistic text, as well as its understanding and perception by the listener as an artistic whole, is a complex aesthetic activity. I. Khovanskaya

singles out the following as the main components of such aesthetic activity: 1) the emergence of artistic images as a result of the author's intention and the aesthetic perception of reality in the mind of the creator; 2) the embodiment of artistic images in aesthetic material, i.e. their modification through the means of the appropriate art type and the creation of a work of art as a product of aesthetic activity; 3) acceptance of the work of art by the public, that is, the process of aesthetic perception. Based on this, he says that literary activity can be imagined as a chain of such relations, that is: the reader of the writing of reality. In the linguopoetic analysis of the literary text, it is necessary to always take into account this kind of chain. [1, 96]

Since the artistic text itself is extremely complex and cannot (and should not) be interpreted in the same way by its readers and perceivers, a clear model of its linguopoetic analysis has not been created. . In the practice of linguistics and language education, specific principles and methods of investigation such as phonetic analysis, morphological analysis or syn-tactic analysis have stagnated. But in linguopoetics it has not yet reached this level. Linguistic principles of artistic text are generally recommended in various educational literature. In Uzbek philology, M. Yokubbekova tried to develop the principles of linguopoetic analysis of folk songs, it can be said that she managed to define effective principles in this regard.

Based on our observations, it is possible to single out the following as the main principles of linguopoetic interpretation of the artistic text. [3, 120]

Artistic style (the function of influencing language, promotion, agitation) - covers all aspects of human life. This style differs from other styles in that it is equal to everyone, and has an emotional impact on the reader and listener. In this style, the author can use all the lexical and grammatical tools of the language, leaving various expressive tools. Materials of other styles can be freely used in artistic style. Accordingly, artistic style is a type of style with wide possibilities. The artistic style is characteristic of fiction, that is, artistic works, in which artistry, expressiveness, and impressiveness are strong. The unique feature of the artistic style is that, along with incorporating all the possibilities of the literary language, lexical units related to Uzbek dialects, professions, and historical words that are out of use today are also used through the speech of the characters. The artistic style arouses aesthetic pleasure in the reader. Therefore, the speech realized through the artistic style, in addition to providing information about a certain event (communicative task), also performs the task of influencing the reader (expressive). Figurative and aesthetic effect is an important sign of artistic style. The study of the artistic style is not limited to the field of music, figurative thinking, and from the functional point of view. Its scope of content is extremely wide and it is created as a result of symbols, artistic texture, writer's fantasy. Prose, poetry and dramatic works are created in the artistic style. Artistic style arises in the relationship between image, creativity and personality. In the artistic style, words and phrases belonging to all layers of the national language and literary language are widely and actively used and perform the function of aesthetic impression. [4, 23]

A work of art, that is, an artistic text, is a complex and multifaceted aesthetic whole that is absolutely unique in both form and content. If the content is as important as the content, the form is equally important. In other words, it can be said that sometimes the form can rise to the level of the content, take the meaning of the content, and actually touch the value of the content (with the requirement of artistic purpose). Of course, the law of the dialectical unity of

form and content, which is always manifested in one way or another in every phenomenon of nature and society, big or small, is not alien to the artistic text. But this dialectical regularity lives in a complete work of art in a truly unique way, in a state unlike any other phenomenon of nature and society.

As a conclusion, it can be said that considering the language in an artistic text as only form, and the series of events expressed in it as content, imagining the unity and proportionality of form and content in an artistic work only in such a dichotomy is nothing more than revitalizing the essence of the art of artistic words. In a literary text, the author's ability to shape the content, individual characteristics in it have a special value. As V. Odintsov rightly noted, the emotional-artistic structure in the artistic text transforms the "natural" (i.e., reflecting the real connections and relationships of concepts) logical structures, therefore, the form in the artistic work is of great importance compared to other works. The truth is that not only in poetry, but also in prose, changing the form means destroying and killing the text. But based on this, the form cannot be considered primary and the content secondary in an artistic text, both of them are important, only the manner of manifestation of the dialectical relationship between them is unique. [5, 67]

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